

A Note on Numbers

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ABSTRACT:

A Fermat number is a number of the form $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1$, where n is an integer ≥ 0 . A Fermat composite (see [1] or [2] or [4]) is a non prime Fermat number and a Fermat prime is a prime Fermat number. Fermat composites and Fermat primes are characterized via divisibility in [4] and in [5]. It is known (see [4]) that for every $j \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$, F_j is a Fermat prime and it is also known (see [2] or [3]) that F_5 and F_6 are Fermat composites. In this paper, we show [via elementary arithmetic congruences] the following result (E.). For every integer $n > 0$ such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, we have $F_{n-1} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$; and for every integer $n \geq 2$, we have $F_{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$, where $j \in \{3, 5\}$. Result (E.) immediately implies that there are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $2 + F_n$. Result (E.) also implies that the only prime of the form $4 + F_n$ is 7 and the only primes of the form $8 + F_n$ are twin primes 11 and 13. That being said, using result (E.) and a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet, we explain why it is natural to conjecture that there are infinitely many primes of the form $2 + F_n$.

Keywords: Fermat numbers, F_n .

AMS Classification 2000: 11xx

Suggested Citation: I. Annouk, "A Note on Numbers," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(2), pp. 330-333, Mar-Apr 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).24](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).24)

THEOREM 1.1.

(E.). For every integer $n > 0$ such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, we have $F_n - 1 \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$; and for every integer $n \geq 2$, we have $F_n - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$, where $j \in \{3, 5\}$.

(E.1). There are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $2 + F_n$.

(E.2). The only prime of the form $4 + F_n$ is 7 and the only primes of the form $8 + F_n$ are twin primes 11 and 13.

To prove Theorem 1.1, we need the following remarks.

Remark 1.0. Let n be an integer > 1 such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. If $2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$, then $2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$. (Proof. Immediate [indeed observe (via elementary arithmetic congruences) that $2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 256 \pmod{7}$ (since $2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$) and $256 \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$].)

Proposition 1.1. Let n be an integer > 0 such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$;

then $2^{2^n} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$.

(Proof. Otherwise

$$\text{let } n \text{ be minimum such that } 2^{2^n} \not\equiv 4 \pmod{7} \text{ (} n \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ and } n > 0 \text{)} \quad (1.1)$$

Clearly

$$n \geq 3 \tag{1.2}$$

(since $2^{2^1} = 4$ and $4 \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$). It is immediate to see that

$$2^{2^n} = 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \tag{1.3}$$

Now using equality (1.3) and inequality (1.2), we easily deduce that (1.1) clearly implies that

$$2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \not\equiv 4 \pmod{7}; 2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 4 \pmod{7} (n \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ and } n > 1) \tag{1.4}$$

(1.4) clearly contradicts Remark 1.0.)

Remark 1.2. Let n be an integer ≥ 3 . If $2^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$ where $j \in \{3, 5\}$, then $2^{2^{n-1}} \times 2^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$.
(**Proof.** Immediate [via elementary arithmetic congruences].)

Proposition 1.3. Let n be an integer ≥ 2 ; then $2^{2^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$, where $j \in \{3, 5\}$.

(**Proof.** Otherwise

$$\text{let } n \text{ be minimum such that } 2^{2^n} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{j} \text{ where } j \in \{3, 5\} \tag{1.5}$$

Clearly

$$n \geq 3 \tag{1.6}$$

(since $2^{2^2} = 16$ and $16 \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$ where $j \in \{3, 5\}$). It is immediate to see that

$$2^{2^n} = 2^{2^{n-1}} \times 2^{2^{n-1}} \tag{1.7}$$

Now using equality (1.7) and inequality (1.6), we easily deduce that (1.5) clearly implies that

$$2^{2^{n-1}} \times 2^{2^{n-1}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{j}, \text{ where } j \in \{3, 5\} \text{ and where } 2^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}; n \geq 3 \tag{1.8}.$$

(1.8) clearly contradicts Remark 1.2.)

Proposition 1.4. Let n be an integer ≥ 3 such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Then $2 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$ and $2 + F_n$ is composite.

(**Proof.** Clearly

$$2 + (2^{2^n} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{7} \tag{1.9}$$

[observe that $2^{2^n} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$ (use Proposition 1.1) and use elementary arithmetic congruences]. So $2 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$ and $2 + F_n$ is composite [use congruence (1.9) and observe that $2+(2^{2^n} + 1) = 2+F_n$ and $2+F_n > 7$ (note that $n \geq 3$)]. Proposition 1.4 immediately follows).

Proposition 1.5. Let n be an integer ≥ 2 . Then $4 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $4 + F_n$ is composite.

(**Proof.** Clearly

$$4 + (2^{2^n} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \quad (1.10)$$

[observe that $2^{2^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ (use Proposition 1.3) and use elementary arithmetic congruences]. So $4 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $4 + F_n$ is composite [use congruence (1.10) and observe that $4+(2^{2^n} + 1) = 4+F_n$ and $4+F_n > 3$ (note that $n \geq 2$)]. Proposition 1.5 immediately follows).

Proposition 1.6. Let n be an integer ≥ 2 . Then $8 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ and $8 + F_n$ is composite.

(**Proof.** Clearly

$$8 + (2^{2^n} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{5} \quad (1.11)$$

[observe that $2^{2^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$ (use Proposition 1.3) and use elementary arithmetic congruences]. So $8 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ and $8 + F_n$ is composite [use congruence (1.11) and observe that $8+(2^{2^n} + 1) = 8+F_n$ and $8+F_n > 5$ (note that $n \geq 2$)]. Proposition 1.6 immediately follows).

Remark 1.7. There are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $2 + F_n$ or there are infinitely many prime numbers of the form $2 + F_n$.

(**Proof.** Immediate).

Having made the previous Remarks and Propositions, then Theorem 1.1 becomes immediate to prove.

PROOF OF THEOREM 1.1

(**E.**) Immediate [use Proposition 1.1 and Proposition 1.3 and observe that $2^{2^n} = F_n - 1$].

(**E.1.**) Immediate [use Proposition 1.4 and Remark 1.7].

(**E.2.**) Clearly the only prime of the form $4 + F_n$ is 7 [observe that $4 + F_0 = 7$ and $4 + F_1 = 9$ and use Proposition 1.5]; and clearly the only primes of the form $8 + F_n$ are twin primes 11 and 13 [observe that $8 + F_0 = 11$ and $8 + F_1 = 13$ and use Proposition 1.6].

Now usig Result (**E.**), then we end this paper by looking at numbers of the form $2 + F_n$ which are prime [observe that for every $n \in \{0, 1, 2, 4\}$, $2 + F_n$ is prime and $2 + F_3$ is not prime].

Observation. It is natural to conjecture that there are infinitely many primes of the form $2 + F_n$.

Indeed observing [via Result (**E.**) of Theorem 1.1] that

$$F_n - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \text{ and } F_n - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \text{ for every integer } n \geq 2 \quad (1.12),$$

Clearly

$$2 + F_n \equiv 4 \pmod{5} \text{ and } 2 + F_n \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \text{ for every integer } n \geq 2 \quad (1.13)$$

[use (1.12) and elementary arithmetic congruences].

Now let $A_{4,5} = \{e; e \text{ is prime and } e \equiv 4 \pmod{5}\}$ and let $A_{1,3} = \{e'; e' \text{ is prime and } e' \equiv 1 \pmod{3}\}$.

Since it is immediate that

$$(4, 5) = 1 \text{ and } (1, 3) = 1 \tag{1.14}$$

then using (1.14) coupled with a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet, it follows that

$$\text{card}(A_{4,5}) \text{ is infinite and } \text{card}(A_{1,3}) \text{ is infinite} \tag{1.15}$$

Now using (1.13) and (1.15) and the fact that for every $n \in \{0, 1, 2, 4\}$, $2 + F_n$ is prime, then it becomes naturel to conjecture the following.

CONJECTURE

$A_{4,5} \cup A_{1,3}$ contains infinitely many numbers of the form $2 + F_n$ ($A_{4,5}$ and $A_{1,3}$ are defined via the Observation placed just above).

The previous conjecture immediately implies that there are infinitely many primes of the form $2 + F_n$.

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